

**BUSSINESKA TIPIDAGI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN NOLOKAL
CHEGARAVIY MASALANING YECHIMI**

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Annotatsiya: Bu ishda ko'p o'lchovli sohada Bussineska tipidagi differensial tenglama uchun nolokal masalani qaradik. Echimning spektral yoyilmasi, mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: nolokal masala, Bussineska tipidagi tenglama, ko'p o'lchovli soha, spectral yoyilma, yechim.

Masalaning qo'yilishi

Aytaylik $\Omega \subset \mathbf{R}^n$ - $\partial\Omega$ silliq chegaraga ega va $T>0$ ixtiyoriy chegaralangan soha bo'lsin. $\Omega \times (0, T)$ tsilindirdagi quydagi quydagi tenglamani qaraymiz:

$$u_{tt} - \Delta u_{tt} - \nu^2 \Delta u = f(x), \quad x \in \Omega, \quad 0 < t < T, \quad (1)$$

ν - musbat son.

A - Laplas operatorining ixtiyoriy musbat o'z-o'ziga qo'shma kengaytmasi

$$-\Delta : Au = -\Delta u, \quad u \in C_0^\infty(\Omega),$$

$$(Au, u) \geq \mu(u, u), \quad \mu > 0, \quad u \in D(A).$$

Deylik, A operatorining A^{-1} kompakt teskari operatori bor. Ayniqsa, bu o'z-o'ziga qoshma kengaytma bir qancha $\alpha(x)$ va $\beta(x)$ ga mos quydagi chegaraviy shartlar bilan yaratilishi mumkin

$$\alpha(x) \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} + \beta(x)u = 0, \quad x \in \partial\Omega, \quad (2)$$

Quydagi nolokal shartlarni qaraymiz

$$u(x, 0) = u(x, T), \quad (3)$$

$$\int_0^T u(x, t) dt = \phi(x). \quad (4)$$

Bu ishdagi asosiy maqsad (3) va (4) boshlangich shartlar bilan berilgan (1) tenglamaning yechimini topish va yechimning konstruktiv tuzilishini tadqiq qilishdan iborat.

(1), (3) va (4) masalaning yechimini $u(x, t)$ funksiya ko'rinishida aniqlaymiz:

- 1) $0 \leq t \leq T$ oraliqdan olingan har bir t uchun $D(A)$ sohaga tegishli va $L_2(\Omega)$ normadagi shu sohada t bo'yicha uzluksiz;
- 2) $L_2(\Omega)$ normadagi $(0, T)$ ochiq intervalda $Au(x, t)$ funksiyasi bilan ikki karra differensiallanuvchi;
- 3) (3) va (4) shartlar bilan berilgan (1) masalani qnoatlantiradi.

Yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligini isbotlash uchun bazi muhim parametrlarni kiritamiz. To'plam $\theta(\nu) = \frac{\nu T}{2\pi}$ ga teng. λ_k va $\nu_k(x)$ o'z-o'ziga qo'shma A operatorning xos qiymatlari va xos funksiyalari bo'lsin:

$$A\nu_k(x) = \lambda_k \nu_k(x), \quad x \in \Omega. \quad (5)$$

Biz to'plamni quydagicha ta'riflaymiz

Ixtiyoriy $\phi(x) \in L_2(\Omega)$ funksiyaning spektral yoyilmasi quydagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi

$$\phi(x) \in L_2(\Omega) \quad \phi(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \phi_k v_k(x), \quad \phi_k = (\phi, v_k).$$

Bizning taxminimizga ko'ra

$$\mu \leq \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \dots \leq \lambda_k \rightarrow \infty.$$

Shunda

$$v_k = v \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_k}{1 + \lambda_k}}. \quad (6)$$

Bu ishda quydagi teoremaning to'g'riligi isbotlangan.

Teorema. Aytaylik $0 < \theta(v) < 1$ va $\phi \in D(A)$ bo'lsin. Unda (3) va (4) shartlar berilgan (1) masalaning yechimi mavjud va yagona bo'ladi.

Eslatma. Agar Laplas operatorining o'z-o'ziga qo'shma kengaytmasi Dirixle chegaraviy masalasi bilan hosil qilingan bo'lsa, (yana (2)da $\alpha = 0$ va $\beta = 1$ bo'lsa) unda $D(A) = W_2^2(\Omega) \cap \overset{0}{W}_2^1$ bo'ladi.

Ish quydagicha tashkil qilingan. Biz 2 qismda A o'z-o'ziga qo'shma operatorining xos funksiyalariga bog'liq, yechimning spektral yoyilmasini topamiz.

3-qismda bo'lsa asosiy keltirilgan teoremani isbotini qaraymiz.

Yechimning spektral yoyilmasi

Biz (1) ko'rinishdagi masalani quydagicha yozsak bo'ladi:

$$(I + A)u_{tt} + \nu^2 Au = f(x)$$

yoki

$$u_{tt} + \nu^2 A(I + A)^{-1}u = (I + A)^{-1}f(x), \quad x \in \Omega, \quad 0 < t < T. \quad (7)$$

Faraz qilaylik $u(x, t)$ (7), (3) va (4) masalaning yechimi. Shunga ko'ra yechimning spektral yoyilmasi quydagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C_k(t)v_k(x), \quad (8)$$

Bu yerda

$$C_k(t) = (u, v_k) = \int u(x, t)v_k(x, t)dx$$

(7) tenglamani $v_k(x)$ ga ko'paytirib, quydagi ko'rinishga keltiramiz:

$$(u_{tt}, v_k) + \nu^2 (A(I + A)^{-1}u, v_k) = ((I + A)^{-1}f(x), v_k) \quad (9)$$

Yechimning ta'rifiga ko'ra

$$(u_{tt}, v_k) = \frac{d^2}{dt^2} (u, v_k) = C_k''(t).$$

Eslatib o'tamiz A o'z-o'ziga qo'shma operator. (5) tenglamani hisobga olib quydagi ko'rinishda yozishimiz mumkin:

$$(A(I + A)^{-1}u, v_k) = (u, A(I + A)^{-1}v_k) = \frac{\lambda_k}{1 + \lambda_k} (u, v_k) = \frac{\lambda_k}{1 + \lambda_k} C_k(t)$$

$$((I + A)^{-1} f(x), v_k) = (f(x), (I + A)^{-1} v_k) = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_k} (f(x), v_k) = \tilde{f}$$

(6)dagi belgilashni hisobga olsak

$$v_k^2 (A(I + A)^{-1} u, v_k) = v_k^2 C_k(t). \quad (10)$$

ko'rinishga kelamiz.

Demak, (9) va (10) nan $C_k''(t) + v_k^2 C_k(t) = \tilde{f}$ tenglama o'rinli ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Bu kelib chiqqan bir jinsli bo'lmagan oddiy differensial tenglanaming umumiy yechimi

$$C_k(t) = a_k \cos v_k t + b_k \sin v_k t + \tilde{C}(t)$$

bo'ladi. Bu yerda xususiy yechim

$$\tilde{C}(t) = \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2}$$

ga teng. Demak, umumiy yechim quydagicha bo'ladi

$$C_k(t) = a_k \cos v_k t + b_k \sin v_k t + \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2} \quad (11)$$

Biz endi bu tenglamaga (3) va (4) shartlarni qo'llaymiz:

$$C_k(0) = C_k(T) \quad (12)$$

$$\int_0^T C_k(t) dt = \phi_k \quad (13)$$

(12) ni hisobga olib, quydagi tenglikga kelamiz

$$a_k + \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2} = a_k \cos v_k T + b_k \sin v_k T + \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2}.$$

Keyin bu tenglikni soddalashtirib

$$a_k (1 - \cos v_k T) = b_k \sin v_k T$$

yo'ki

$$a_k \sin^2 \frac{v_k T}{2} = b_k \sin \frac{v_k T}{2} \cos \frac{v_k T}{2} \quad (14)$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'lamiz.

Barcha v_k lar noldan farqli, shunda

$$\sin \frac{v_k T}{2} \neq 0.$$

bo'ladi.

Demak, (14) dan

$$a_k \sin \frac{v_k T}{2} = b_k \cos \frac{v_k T}{2} \quad (15)$$

kelib chiqadi. $\cos \frac{v_k T}{2} \neq 0$ deb olib

$$d_k = \frac{a_k}{\cos \frac{v_k T}{2}} = \frac{b_k}{\sin \frac{v_k T}{2}}$$

belgilash kiritamiz.

d_k ni (11) yechimga oborib qo'ysak, quydagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$C_k(t) = d_k \left(\cos \frac{v_k T}{2} \cos v_k t + \sin \frac{v_k T}{2} \sin v_k t \right) + \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2}$$

va quydagi umumiy yechimga ega bo'lamiz:

$$C_k(t) = d_k \cos \left[v_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] + \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2}. \quad (16)$$

Shunday qilib (8) dagi koeffitsientlar yoyilmasi uchun (16) tenglamaga kelamiz. (13) shartdan biz d_k noma'lum koeffitsientni aniqlaymiz

$$\phi_k = \int_0^T C_k(t) dt = \int_0^T \left[d_k \cos \left[v_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2} \right] dt = \frac{2d_k \sin \frac{v_k T}{2}}{v_k} + \frac{\tilde{f}T}{v_k^2}.$$

Noma'lum koeffitsient d_k quydagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi

$$d_k = \frac{\phi_k v_k^2 - \tilde{f}T}{2v_k \sin \frac{v_k T}{2}} \quad (17)$$

Umumiy qilib aytganda, (3) va (4) shartlar bilan berilgan (1) tenglama yechimga ega bo'ladigan bo'lsa u quydagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\phi_k v_k^2 - \tilde{f}T}{2v_k \sin \frac{v_k T}{2}} \cos \left[v_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] + \frac{\tilde{f}}{v_k^2} \right] v_k(x) \quad (18)$$

Shunday qilib, quydagi tasdiqning to'g'riligi isbotlandi.

Tasdiq 2.1. Aytaylik, $u(x,t) - \phi \in L_2(\Omega)$ funksiya uchun, berilgan (7)+(3)+(4)

ma'salaning yechimi bo'lsin unda uning spektral yoyilmasi (18) ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

Shuni eslatib o'tamizki, $u(x,t)$ funksiyasi ko'rib chiqilayotgan masalaning yechimi bo'lishi uchun u va uning t bo'yicha ikkinchi tartibli hosilasi A operatorining

aniqlanish sohasiga tegishli bo'lishi karak. Quydagi ikkita tasdiq shu shartlarga bog'liq.

Tasdiq 2.2. (18) spektral yoyilma bilan aniqlangan $u(x,t)$ funksiya $t > 0$ ga nisbatan $D(A)$ ga tegishli bo'ladi va faqatgina agar

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[|\phi_k| \lambda_k^2 - \tilde{f}T]^2}{\nu_k^2 \sin^2 \frac{\nu_k T}{2}} < +\infty . \quad (19)$$

bo'lsa.

Isbot. (18) tenglamaga A operatorini qo'llasak quydagi tenglamaga kelamiz

$$Au(x,t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \left[\frac{[\phi_k \nu_k^2 - \tilde{f}T]}{2\nu_k \sin \frac{\nu_k T}{2}} \cos \left[\nu_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] + \frac{\tilde{f}}{\nu_k^2} \right] \nu_k(x) \quad (20)$$

(20) dan

$$\| Au(\cdot, t) \|^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 \left[\frac{[\phi_k \nu_k^2 - \tilde{f}T]}{2\nu_k \sin \frac{\nu_k T}{2}} \cos \left[\nu_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] + \frac{\tilde{f}}{\nu_k^2} \right]^2$$

kelamiz. Quydagi tengsizlik bajarilishi uchun

$$\| Au(\cdot, t) \|^2 \leq \text{const}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

ushbu

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 \left[\frac{[\phi_k \nu_k^2 - \tilde{f}T]}{2\nu_k \sin \frac{\nu_k T}{2}} \cos \left[\nu_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] + \frac{\tilde{f}}{\nu_k^2} \right]^2 \leq \text{const}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (21)$$

shart bajarilishi kerak.

(6) tasdiqdan

$$\frac{\mu}{\mu+1} v^2 \leq v_k^2 < v^2. \quad (22)$$

bo'ladi.

Demak (19) shart bajarilgandagina (21) baho o'rinli bo'ladi.

Tasdiq 2.3. Faraz qilaylik (19) shart bajarilgan bo'lsin. Unda $u(x,t)$ va $Au(x,t)$ funksiyalari $t > 0$ da ikki karra uzluksiz differensiallanuvchi bo'ladi.

Isbot. (20) ni ikki karra differensiallab quydagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} Au(x,t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_k v_k [\phi_k v_k^2 - \tilde{f}T]}{2 \sin \frac{v_k T}{2}} \cos \left[v_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right] v_k(x)$$

Persevalning tengsizligini qo'llab quydagiga kelamiz

$$\left\| \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} Au(\cdot, t) \right\|^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_k^2 v_k^2 [\phi_k v_k^2 - \tilde{f}T]^2}{4 \sin^2 \frac{v_k T}{2}} \cos^2 \left[v_k \left(t - \frac{T}{2} \right) \right]$$

(22) ni hisobga olgan holda, (19) shart bajarilsagina quydagi

$$\left\| \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} Au(x,t) \right\| \leq \text{const}$$

baho o'rinli.

Teoremaning isboti.

$0 < \theta(\nu) < 1$ bo'lganligidan quydagi tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi $0 < \nu T < 2\pi$.

2.2 va 2.3 tasdiqlarga ko'ra, teoremani isbotlash uchun (19) qatorning yaqinlashuvchanligini tekshirish kifoya.

(22) tengsizlikni foydalanib

$$\frac{\sin(\nu_k T / 2)}{\nu_k T / 2} > \frac{\sin(\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\mu+1}} \nu T / 2)}{\nu T / 2}$$

ga kelimiz.

Shuning uchun

$$\sin(\nu_k T / 2) > \frac{\nu_k}{\nu} \sin(\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\mu+1}} \nu T / 2) = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_k}{1+\lambda_k}} \sin(\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\mu+1}} \nu T / 2)$$

o'rinli bo'ladi.

Shuning uchun, quydagi taxmin o'rinli bo'ladi

$$\sin(\nu_k T / 2) > C_\nu(T) > 0, \quad (23)$$

$$C_\nu(T) = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1}{1+\lambda_1}} \sin(\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\mu+1}} \nu T / 2)$$

Taxminga ko'ra, $\phi \in D(A)$. Chunki

$$A\phi(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \phi_k \nu_k(x)$$

qator quydagini anglatadiki

$$\|A\phi\|^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 |\phi_k|^2 < +\infty \quad (24)$$

(23) va (24) dan (17) qator yaqinlashishi kelib chiqadi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI

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